

Virtual mobility grant (VMG) full report: Investigating the seasonal fluctuations of the CHM15K Ceilometer calibration constant

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Abstract

Seasonal fluctuations in the CHM15K (Lufft) ceilometer's calibration constant have been observed through multiple years of data, with uncertainties translating directly into product uncertainties of up to 30-60%. This study contributes to understanding whether these fluctuations are inherent to instrumental factors or due to atmospheric-related phenomena, emphasizing the importance of understanding and mitigating them for accurate measurements. While instrumental properties like temperature and electronics may contribute, divergent results have been found. Collaboration among research groups aims to understand these fluctuations. This study focuses on investigating whether small amounts of undetected atmospheric aerosols contribute to these fluctuations. Synthetic profiles indicate that undetected aerosols within the calibration window and boundary layer loads, can significantly influence the calibration constant, potentially by a factor of 1.2-2. In some test cases, comparison with high-power lidar (Raymetrics) data confirms the presence of residual aerosols during calibration. This suggests that diffuse aerosols present during calibration could explain the observed seasonal cycle. Further research is needed to fully understand the combined influence of instrumental and atmospheric factors on calibration constant variations.

1 Introduction

Multiple year time series reveal a pronounced seasonal cycle in the CHM15K calibration constant retrieved by e-profile or by other networks (e.g. within Alicenet, Bellini et al., 2024ⁱ). The origin of such a variability is still unknown. Currently, the median of this constant is used within E-Profile to retrieve the attenuated backscatter. The uncertainty in the calibration constant translates directly into the uncertainty of the products (reaching up to 30-60%). Therefore, it is crucial to understand whether these seasonal variations of the calibration constant are a true feature of the instrument and should be followed (e.g. by a Kalman-filter-based approach as in e-profile) or if these are due to artifacts that need to be removed before inferring the best-estimate of the calibration constant. The definition of the Lidar constant (L_c) in the algorithms considered in this study are based on the lidar equation (e.g. Klett, 1985ⁱⁱ) including recent corrections (Speidel and Vogelmann, 2023ⁱⁱⁱ). Note that we follow the general convention of L_c denoted as a 'constant', where in reality L_c may not be constant over time (as addressed in this report).

While the variations could be related to instrumental properties (e.g. temperature, electronics) divergent results have been found by different research groups (e.g. TOPROF 2015 VMG by M. Hervo). Changes in the temperature have also been associated to affect the overlap function of the CHM15K (Hervo et. al, 2016^{iv}), which underlines the influence such instrumental parameters can have on the data.

One other or concurrent explanation could be the presence of diffuse aerosols particles in the 'free troposphere', i.e., in the calibration region. Assumption of an aerosol free region would alter the determination of the calibration. Within this VMG scientists from the Met Office (UK), the Alicenet network (Italy), the German weather service (DWD) and Meteo Swiss have collaborated to investigate the seasonal fluctuations.

2 Objective

The main objective is to investigate the CHM15K ceilometer Lc seasonality, and notably whether the seasonal fluctuations of Lc observed could be caused by small amounts of 'undetected' atmospheric aerosols. The fluctuations typically range up to a factor of 3 of the minimum calibration constants. One explanation could be the seasonal variation of distributed aerosols in the atmospheric region (Rayleigh calibration window) usually employed in the calibration procedure.

3 Methods and results

During this study no in-depth assessment of possible correlation between internal/instrumental parameters of the CHM15K has been performed. There seems to be a change in calibration constant when a firmware upgrade is performed. Five example sites within the United Kingdom (UK) are shown in Figure 1, where the firmware upgrade in 2019 from 0.559 to 0.743 resulted in a stepwise increase of the calibration constant. It is therefore necessary to keep in mind that instrumental factors such as the laser stability and internal processing play an important role in the evolution of Lc. Especially drastic and sudden changes can result in a step change of Lc. Therefore, those changes should be tracked, and separate calibration constants need to be used before and after the change. In addition, another VMG about 'Seasonal variation in the Rayleigh calibration factor of Automatic Lidar-Ceilometers: amplitude across Europe and possible explanations' by M. Van Hove has been conducted. They found links to internal parameters such as internal temperature. However, within the study presented here it was decided to focus on the possibility of the influence of atmospheric conditions which is described in the following.

Figure 1: Lidar constant time series for 5 sites within the UK. A step change in the constant is visible in 2019, when the firmware was changed besides the seasonal fluctuations affecting the different locations differently.

The possible influence of ‘undetected’ aerosols has been investigated in a twofold approach:

- Creation of synthetic Ceilometer profiles with varying amounts of aerosols
- Comparison of long-term seasonal variation of aerosol in the Rayleigh calibration window with Raymetrics (higher power) lidar.

3.1 Creation of synthetic Ceilometer profiles with varying amounts of aerosols.

The synthetic spectra are created using code written by H. Diemoz in the programming language ‘R’ and modified by J. Buxmann for various tests within this study. First a range corrected synthetic lidar signal is created with standard Rayleigh atmosphere using Bodhaine, 1999^v to calculate the molecular backscatter. A random increasing noise with increasing height is also introduced using the ‘jitter’ function around the range corrected signal. The magnitude of the noise was chosen to be consistent with previous findings for CHM15K noise structures (e.g. Stachlewska et. al, 2012^{vi})

Then a small amount of atmospheric aerosols (AOD equivalent to 0.01-0.02) are introduced at different heights as described and discussed below. The backward Klettⁱⁱ method is then applied to calculate the lidar constant in the preselected fitting window between 5.5-7.5km (Rayleigh window).

Four main cases are investigated, adding aerosols:

- a) outside the calibration window (Figure 2).
- b) within the calibration window (Figure 3).
- c) within the calibration window as well as below in the boundary layer (Figure 4).
- d) across the whole profile (Figure 5).

Test no. 6: Rayleigh calibration

Figure 2: Synthetic range corrected signal case a) aerosols outside calibration window.

Test no. 7: Rayleigh calibration

Figure 3: Synthetic range corrected signal case b) aerosols inside calibration window.

Test no. 8: Rayleigh calibration

Figure 4: Synthetic range corrected signal case c) aerosols within the calibration window as well as below in the boundary layer.

Test no. 9: Rayleigh calibration

Figure 5: Synthetic range corrected signal case d) aerosols across the whole range.

Case a) has nearly no influence on the L_c while case b) and c) can affect L_c significantly up to a factor of 1.3 for aerosol with $AOD \sim 0.01$ at 1064 nm in the calibration window. Interestingly, the impact on L_c decreases in case c) due to the aerosol below the calibration window. However, cases b) and c) would most likely be disregarded for calibration by the quality screening of the retrieval procedure.

Interestingly, case d) (diffuse aerosol) can cause a significant change in the calibration constant and possibly not be filtered out by the calibration process. The impact on L_c , of the order of magnitude of 1.1 to ~ 3 , depends on the aerosol loads in both the calibration window and below the calibration window.

3.2 Comparison of long-term seasonal variation of aerosol in the Rayleigh calibration window with Raymetrics (higher power) lidar

Within the UK some of the CHM15K stations are collocated with Raymetrics lidars. In contrast to the CHM15K the higher power lidar is calibrated more regularly using the forward Klett retrieval. The methods used to obtain the lidar constant and further parameters such as extinction and backscatter are described in more detail elsewhere (Osborne et al., 2019^{vii}). No direct correlation was found between the Raymetrics L_c in the same calibration window as used for the CHM15k due to laser power fluctuations, frequent flashlamp changes and interrupted operation of the Raymetrics lidars (at Nottingham Figure 6 and Camborne Figure 7).

Figure 6: Calibration constant for Nottingham CHM15K (black squares with error bars) and Raymetrics lidar $\times 10^{11}$ (blue dots). No clear correlation could be found.

Figure 7: Calibration constant for Camborne CHM15K (green squares with error bars) and Raymetrics lidar $\times 10^{11}$ (orange dots: within same 24h period, blue dots: same night). No clear correlation could be found.

Direct comparison of aerosol amount in the CHM15k calibration window for selected cases on coincident nights confirm thin aerosol layers detectable with the Raymetrics lidar. Two examples are shown in more detail in this report. It should be noted that clear outliers already have been filtered out, and the inspected cases relate to very small aerosol (AOD~0.01-0.03) amounts. Nevertheless, a more in depth analysis on the influence of the seasonal cycle is needed.

The first one from May 5th, 2021, at Camborne, reveals the possibility of residual aerosol between 4-7km during the night when the calibration by e-profile was performed. The integrated AOD in this region (Figure 8) is equal to 0.03 at 355nm (lidar wavelength). The AOD and further backscatter values were translated to 1064nm (assuming consistent lidar ratio for both wavelengths) using the AERONET Angstrom exponents for that day. This leads to an AOD=0.011 at 1064nm in the calibration window. While the aerosols are not visible in the backscatter of the CHM15K (Figure 9) or the range corrected signal of the lidar a faint structure can be seen in the volume depolarisation ratio(VDR) contour plot of the lidar(Figure 8).

The second example on May 12th, 2021, shows a similar aerosol layer above ~5km with an integrated AOD of 0.03 (Figure 10). Again, the layer is not visible and unlikely to be detected by the calibration screening of the CHM15K (Figure 11). However, the layer is even more visible in the VDR of the lidar than in the first example. This does not necessary equal to higher amounts of aerosol, but stronger depolarisation of the individual particles as confirmed by the particle depolarisation ratio of 27% (Figure 10) as compared to 5% on the 5th May and similar AOD on both days (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Raymetrics lidar time height profile of range corrected signal and volume depolarisation ratio (top contour plots), as well as aerosol retrieval for Extinction, backscatter, particle depolarisation ratio (PDR), lidar ratio (LR) and Mass concentration.

Figure 9:Camborne CHM15K backscatter time height profile for 6th May 2021.

Camborne Lidar 11 May 2021 23:59 to 07:08

Figure 10: Raymetrics lidar time height profile of range corrected signal and volume depolarisation ratio (top contour plots), as well as aerosol retrieval for Extinction, backscatter, particle depolarisation ratio (PDR), lidar ratio (LR) and Mass concentration.

Figure 11: Camborne CHM15K backscatter time height profile for 12th May 2021.

Integrated extinction (=AOD) of around 0.03 at 355nm as indicated by the two examples shown have been found in the calibration window, the influence of atmospheric aerosols seems to be a likely scenario. Therefore, we increased the amount of artificial aerosol in the synthetic spectra as shown in Figure 12.

Test no. 8: Rayleigh calibration

Figure 12: Synthetic profile with increased amount of aerosol in the calibration window leading to a bigger change in the calibration constant.

Adding additional aerosol consistent with the Raymetrics prediction in the boundary layer as well (up to AOD=0.01 at 1064nm), revealed a factor 2 possible change in the Lc of the CHM15K using the synthetic profiles. It should be noted that more work needs to be done to investigate the exact shape of the profile and influence of various amounts in the boundary layer and Lc window.

4 Summary and Conclusion

An in-depth investigation in the possibility of small amounts of atmospheric aerosols within the calibration window as possible reason for seasonal variation of Lc has been performed. Synthetic profiles revealed that changes in the Lc of a factor of 1.2-2 are likely with either small amount aerosols present throughout the whole profile or within the calibration window and the boundary layer. A comparison with a high power lidar at similar times when

calibration has been performed by the e-profile retrieval revealed small residual aerosols were present on several occasions clearly visible in the lidar VDR.

We can therefore conclude that there are days where the CHM15K calibration is performed by the e-profile retrieval with small amounts of aerosols present. And it is theoretically possible to account for factors of up to 1.2-2 (or possibly higher) change in L_c . Further investigation is needed to confirm this is sufficient to explain the seasonal cycle. In addition, given this work here and the work by M. Van Hove a combination of both internal instrument related parameters as well as atmospheric conditions contribute to the seasonal variations of the calibration constant.

References

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